

The Precedence Effect: Spectral, Temporal, and Intensive Interactions

Julian Grosse¹⁾, Constantine Trahiotis²⁾, Armin Kohlrausch³⁾, Steven van de Par¹⁾

¹⁾ Carl von Ossietzky Universitaet, Cluster of Excellence Hearing4All, Oldenburg, Germany.

julian.grosse@uol.de, steven.van.de.par@uol.de

²⁾ University of Connecticut Health Center, USA

³⁾ Technische Universiteit Eindhoven, Netherlands

Summary

Within the phenomenon termed the precedence effect, location dominance of the leading signal has been associated with the time-course of spatial cues, with stimulus onset playing a dominant role. For a continuous stimulus consisting of lead and lag components, each with different interaural delays, a pattern of interaural level differences and interaural time delays will be created that varies in a specific manner as a function of frequency. In principle, provided that a sufficiently large spectral interval is available, this type of frequency dependence allows one to infer the direction of the leading sound source. We investigated precedence using such lead-lag stimuli and asked listeners to judge the lateral position(s) of the stimuli, depending on spectral content. Results suggest that with such stimuli, lateralization is dominated by interaural cues available within and across auditory filters. In addition, the data suggest there exists a ‘lateralization bias’ that depends on the patterning of interaural cues that exist across frequency.

© 2018 The Author(s). Published by S. Hirzel Verlag · EAA. This is an open access article under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

PACS no. 43.66.-x, 43.66.Ba, 43.66.Pn, 43.66.Qp

1. Introduction

Classically, the precedence effect has been studied via earphones using pairs of leading and lagging clicks with click-pairs having opposing interaural delays [1]. When lead-lag delays are in the range of 1 to 5 ms or so, the two pairs of clicks are perceptually fused and laterality is dominated by the leading click pair. Interestingly, for continuous stimuli, longer lead-lag times may still create lateralization dominance of the leading signal. Some explanations of the precedence effect pinpoint the time course of spatial cues as allowing for more weight to be placed on interaural cues that occur at the onset of the stimulus [2]. Alternatively, it has been suggested that hair-cell adaptation within the auditory periphery plays a role [3].

Important for the purpose of this study, Dizon and Colburn [4] have shown that the precedence effect can also be observed with continuous stimuli that do not produce onset-related cues specific to the lead stimulus only. Dizon and Colburn effectively convolved pairs of left/right clicks with broad-band noise in order to produce a continuous dichotic noise that, at its onset, contained an Interaural Time Delay (ITD) associated with the leading click

pair. Interestingly and importantly, however, leading stimuli dominated laterality even when the onsets and offsets of the entire stimulus were removed by simultaneously gating the left and right ear signals. Two types of hypotheses appear to us to be helpful for gaining an understanding of this counter-intuitive result. First, although the stimulus onset was removed via simultaneous gating, inherent fluctuations within the noise could have led to micro-transients that could perhaps elicit the precedence effect. Secondly, Braasch [5] suggested that lagging signals may be reduced in strength via a cancellation filter whose presence would allow the leading signal to dominate laterality. It occurred to us that the spectral pattern of interaural cues conveyed by continuous stimuli may vary in a manner that is informative regarding perceived laterality. Such a hypothesis is consistent with analyses of such stimuli that were presented by Zurek [2].

Figure 1 shows the spectral pattern of binaural cues for two pairs of clicks having a lead-lag time of 2 ms and ITDs of 0.3 ms favoring left and right ears, respectively. The top-panel shows the magnitude spectra of the left (solid line) and right (dashed line) ear stimuli. Note that the differentially delayed pairs of clicks combine to produce two comb-filtered spectra, one for each ear. In this example the left click pair leads, causing the (monaural) delay between the leading and lagging clicks to be larger in the left ear than the (monaural) delay between the leading and

Received 2 March 2018,
accepted 3 August 2018.

lagging clicks in the right ear. As a consequence, the patterning of notches occurring in the left-ear's comb-filter is 'denser'. The middle panel shows Interaural Level Differences (ILDs) derived from the left and right ear magnitude spectra. As can be seen, although ILDs vary considerably as a function of frequency, they do not consistently favor either the leading or lagging ear.

Interaural phase differences that were derived from the phase spectra of the left and right ear signals are presented in the lower panel. Note that, for low frequencies (below the first notch), Interaural Phase Differences (IPDs) are equal to zero. Also note that for spectral frequencies beyond the first notch in the left ear, the left ear signal is inverted in phase, leading to an ambiguous IPD of $\pm\pi$. For successive further notches, the IPD alternates between 0 and $\pm\pi$. This patterning of IPDs is consistent with the correlational analysis for similar stimuli presented by Dizon and Colburn [4]. We wished to test the hypothesis that listeners use the specific pattern of binaural cues that occurs in these types of stimuli in order to determine which ear leads.

2. Experiment I: Spectral variations

We designed an experiment using stimuli such as the ones shown in Figure 1 in order to evaluate whether listeners could use such patterns of binaural cues to judge the laterality of the leading part of the compound stimulus. Five young adults served as listeners. All had self-reported normal hearing. Stimuli were presented via Sennheiser HD650 headphones at 65 dB SPL. On each trial, listeners first heard a diotic anchor stimulus followed after 400 ms by one particular lead-lag stimulus combination and were asked to indicate perceived location using a visual pointer on a graphical user interface. They made their responses on a schematic head having ears positioned at each side. The schematic head included a line connecting the two ears and the positions of the left and right ears were rated as -1 and 1, respectively. Previous experiments in our lab (cf. [6]) revealed that listeners can, with increasing Inter-Stimulus Interval (ISI), perceive split images, one located near the position of the leading stimulus and the second located near the position of the lagging stimulus. Consequently, we asked our listeners to make two responses, the first pointing to the more dominant image. When they heard only one image they were instructed to point twice to the same location. The stimuli were two identical band-pass filtered white Gaussian noises, presented in lead-lag fashion. The leading noise was presented with an ITD of $-300 \mu\text{s}$ (left ear leading). The lagging noise had an ITD of $+300 \mu\text{s}$ and was presented after an inter-stimulus interval (ISI) of 2 ms. The noises were gated on and off simultaneously using 20 ms-long raised-cosine ramps and had a total duration of 500 ms. In addition to a wideband noise ranging from 100 Hz to 1 kHz, several ERB_N -wide filtered versions of the stimuli were employed at each of 12 center frequencies spanning the range from 100 Hz to 1 kHz in accordance with [7] assuming normal hearing. Stimu-

Figure 1. Frequency dependence of the magnitude spectrum (top panel), ILDs (middle panel), and IPDs (lower panel).

Figure 2. Data obtained in experiment I with narrowband and wideband noise stimuli presented with fixed inter-stimulus-interval of 2 ms. The sizes of the symbols reflect the relative frequency of single (circles) vs. split images (triangles). Dashed lines show the adjusted positions for single $\pm 300 \mu\text{s}$ delayed noises also obtained in our experiments.

lus conditions were run in a random order in a block-wise manner and were repeated three times.

2.1. Results

Figure 2 shows the results of experiment I. The reader is reminded that the ISI was 2 ms and the spectral content of the noise was varied in terms of center frequency. As expected, the listeners often reported two (split) images. The proximity of the two responses was analyzed for each trial in order to assess the relative frequency of one image or two images. If the distance between the two responses was less than 0.05 su (scale units), it was assumed that the listener perceived one image. The relative frequency of single and dual images is reflected by the sizes of symbols in the figure. The data in the figure represent the mean positions of the two types of responses. The right-most data point represents the perceived lateralization of the wide band noise. Note that it was perceived predominantly towards the lateral position of the leading signal (i.e., left) when presented alone, as indicated by the dashed horizontal lines. Also note that the data obtained with narrow-band noises show two trends: 1) sizable changes in perceived laterality produced by changes in center frequency and 2) the degree to which relatively infrequently occurring split images were heard. Specifically for center frequencies of

Figure 3. Predictions based on mean-weighted ILDs (open triangles) or including an additional bias based on the spectral patterning of ILD and IPD cues (open squares). The solid circles depict the single image data shown in Figure 2

209 Hz and 259 Hz, split images were heard on 87% and 60% of the presentations, respectively.

The patterning of the data in Figure 2 clearly indicates that the narrowband noise stimuli which were presented without onsets and offsets did not show lateralization dominance; i.e. lateralization towards the ITD of the leading portions of the stimuli (in accordance with the precedence effect). This suggests that momentarily-occurring variations within the temporal structure of the ongoing stimulus are not, by themselves, sufficient for elicitation of the precedence effect. It should be stressed that this view may not be generalizable to stimuli spanning bandwidths larger than one ERB_N . It could be the case that the relatively narrow bandwidths of each ERB_N limit the rate of changes of interaural cues.

2.2. Interpretation and modeling of the data

We first attempted to predict perceived lateral position by calculating the mean across the specific-loudness-weighted ILDs that were present at each center frequency (i.e. within auditory filter). In order to do so we employed a bank of 150 overlapping ERB_N -wide filters having center frequencies from 80 Hz to 1.6 kHz. Interaural temporal differences were not considered because, for these particular stimulus conditions they do not point to any specific direction. The mean-weighted ILDs were divided by 20 dB so that predictions would cover the same range of the -1 to 1 scale present in the listeners' responses. These predictions are indicated by the diamonds in Figure 3. The predictions capture many of the trends shown by the patterning of the data. Those successes notwithstanding, the lateralized positions of stimuli having center frequencies of 259 Hz and 703 Hz, and the wide band noise, were considerably more toward the leading ear (left ear) than was the position of the image predicted via mean-weighted ILDs. As shown in Figure 1, our stimuli centered at 259 Hz and 703 Hz possess extremely large interaural phase shifts that would, in and of themselves, result in ambiguous information within the cross-correlation surface commonly used to interpret binaural localization. As discussed by Buell *et al.* [8] such ambiguous cross-correlations are 'labile' in that

perceived location is strongly affected by small amounts of ILD and/or onset information.

As can be seen in Figure 1, large reversals of IPD were accompanied by ILDs shifting towards the leading (left) ear with increasing frequency. Note that this occurred at center frequencies near 250 Hz, 750 Hz, and a range of center frequencies between 1100 and 1500 Hz. If the stimuli were completely reversed vis a vis left and right ears, this patterning would reverse and ILDs would then increase towards the right with increasing frequency. In order to take this into account, we implemented a 'lateralization bias' such that whenever the IPD approached $\pm\pi$, a bias was assumed to occur having a magnitude and direction as indicated by the spectral derivative of the ILD. The bias was implemented according to the following rule:

$$\text{bias} = -\alpha \frac{\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \Delta \text{ILD}(k) \cdot N'(k) \cdot \sigma_{\text{IPD}}(k)}{\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K N'(k)}. \quad (1)$$

Here $\alpha = 10$ dB is a scaling factor. The difference, Δ , of ILDs across subsequent channels is taken, and the standard deviation σ of IPDs within a specific frequency channel (indexed with k) is used. The variable $N'(k)$ denotes specific loudness within each channel. Mean loudness-weighted values are calculated across K channels by first adding the left and right ear powers, and then using the resulting sum $S(k)$ to calculate: $N'(k) = \max(S(k)^{0.3}, 1) - 1$. The open squares in Figure 3 display predictions that include the added bias calculated via Eq. 1. The predictions improve, especially for data obtained at center frequencies of 259 Hz, and 703 Hz, and for the wideband condition. Also note that the addition of the bias shifted the predictions more towards the left, leading ear. This outcome illustrates the advantage of utilizing a lateralization bias derived from the spectral pattern of interaural cues in order to capture the degree to which perceived laterality favors the leading sound source. Said differently, the effect of the lateralization bias is to account for the degree to which precedence affects lateral position.

3. Experiment II: Cues at onset

A second control experiment was conducted to determine whether simultaneous onset-offset gating of leading and lagging stimuli substantially influences perceived laterality in stimulus conditions typically used to study precedence. The 5 listeners who participated in Experiment I also participated in this experiment. We employed the same wide band noise employed in Experiment I either with or without simultaneous gating in each ear and with ISIs varying from 0 ms to 10 ms. In addition, we collected data employing two dichotic pairs of 150 μs duration clicks having spectral content from 100 Hz to 1 kHz, with ISI varying from 0 ms to 10 ms and with opposing ITDs of $\pm 300 \mu\text{s}$ (as was done in Experiment I).

Figure 4. Data obtained in experiment II for a click stimulus (left panel), gated noise (mid panel) and non-gated noise stimuli (right panel). Illustrated are mean values for all ISIs across all responses which were grouped in one single image (circle) and two split images (triangles).

3.1. Results

The three panels in Figure 4 show the means of the listeners' responses which were obtained while employing either pairs of clicks, interaurally simultaneously gated bands of noise, and band of noise having onsets of leading and lagging stimuli. As can be seen in the left-most panel of Figure 4, the majority of the stimuli having ISIs from 1 to 3 ms were perceived as having split images. The dominant image (i.e. the one the listeners reported first) was perceived towards the leading ear, in accord with precedence. The second image was reported to be near mid-line. When ISIs were increased towards 10 ms, the listeners indicated split images commensurate with the $\pm 300 \mu\text{s}$ stimulus ITDs. Note that the data presented in the middle and right-hand panels indicate two important departures. First, single (fused) images indicating precedence (i.e. images towards the leading ear) were perceived for ISIs between 1 and 5 ms for interaurally simultaneously gated stimuli (middle panel) and for ISIs between 1 and 8 ms for non-gated stimuli (right panel, leading ITD cues present at the onset). Secondly, split images began to occur at smaller ISIs for gated stimuli (middle panel), in comparison with their non-gated counterparts (right-most panel). The overall patterning of the data indicates that the presence of onsets and offsets within broadband noise stimuli does not influence greatly the degree to which the stimuli elicit precedence but does affect whether split images are heard at large ISIs.

4. Summary and conclusions

We found that the patterning of interaural cues that occurs as a function of center frequency is highly informative regarding the direction of images reported by listeners

in a paradigm commonly used to study the precedence effect. Successful predictions of the data were obtained by assessing the filter-by-filter presence of interaural cues produced within the ongoing portions of the narrow-band stimuli presented in lead-lag configurations. In addition, we found that predictions of perceived laterality could be improved if a type of 'lateralization bias' was taken into account. The bias was implemented according to a simple formulation which considered the patterning of ILDs that occurred in spectral locations which conveyed ambiguous IPDs (ITDs). Currently we are conducting research targeted towards revealing more precisely how perceived lateralization may depend on the spectral patterning of interaural cues. In addition, we are planning to conduct experiments that will help determine the degree to which the phenomena discussed here may be useful for understanding localization measured in more complex acoustic situations, especially those in which the stimuli contain information provided by the presence of multiple reflections. Finally, we believe that it will be interesting and useful to evaluate whether the ideas presented herein can be successfully incorporated into modern cross-correlation-based models of binaural hearing (rather than being considered primarily at cue level).

References

- [1] H. Wallach, E. Newman, M. R. Rosenzweig: A precedence effect in sound localization. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **21** (1949) 468–468.
- [2] P. M. Zurek: The precedence effect and its possible role in the avoidance of interaural ambiguities. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **67** (1980) 952–964.
- [3] K. Hartung, C. Trahiotis: Peripheral auditory processing and investigations of the "precedence effect" which utilize successive transient stimuli. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **110** (2001) 1505–1513.
- [4] R. M. Dizon, H. S. Colburn: The influence of spectral, temporal, and interaural stimulus variations on the precedence effect. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **119** (2006) 2947–2964.
- [5] J. Braasch: A precedence effect model to simulate localization dominance using an adaptive, stimulus parameter-based inhibition process. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **134** (2013) 420–435.
- [6] J. Grosse, S. van de Par, C. Trahiotis: Stimulus coherence influences sound-field localization and fusion/segregation of leading and lagging sounds. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **141** (2017) 2673–2680.
- [7] B. R. Glasberg, B. C. J. Moore: Derivation of auditory filter shapes from notched-noise data. *Hearing Res.* **47** (1990) 103–138.
- [8] T. N. Buell, C. Trahiotis, L. R. Bernstein: Lateralization of bands of noise as a function of combinations of interaural intensive differences, interaural temporal differences, and bandwidth. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **95** (1994) 1482–1489.